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Communication Fusion And Fission

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Abstract

The current study is limited to the contemporary reflection in the sciences of communication on how to communicate, how to read the context of communication, how everything that happens to us appears as a satu text as a set of texts, how differences, dissensions and conflicts are radically different readings of the same reality. The core of communication is understanding. The theme of this research is the relationship between what the sender communicator produces and what the recipient understands. The processes of formulation, fusion and fission of meanings form the core of the activity of communication-producing thinking. In relation to these, the performance of communication in the realization of meaningful communication can be evaluated.

Keywords: communicator, communication, meaning fusion, meaning fission, communion

1. Introduction

People are producers of messages in the form of texts, messages, remarks, which appear as speeches. We don't always read the same text. Reading subsumes a collection: we read at sea, each time, a different text. As changing readers, we are confronted with texts that implicitly change significantly by deepening reading and changing the reading self. The current reading is a perishable reading of a passing reader. Plural and multimodal reading is a reading that better covers the flow of significant fusion and fission. Each reading is a new and in new parameters significant fission. Each reading is a specific challenge to the textual meaning.

2. Forms and language

Any discourse is the specific formulation of a cognitive, emotional, volitional content, etc. As such, it should be treated as an update of one of the many potential formulations. For a certain communicative content, an expression is chosen, an appearance from the multitude of possible formulations. Some forms of communication are colloquial, some literary, some scientific, some journalistic. Some aim to highlight an idea, a particular aspect of the amount of knowledge. Others focus on highlighting another aspect. Some of those who make speeches focus on elements of one kind, others on elements of another kind. Thus, several communicators who talk about one and the same subject, event, situation will write about these different discourses. The different texts, without being false, will be only partially equivalent: in the area of objective, universal meanings. Even within the same register or style, the wording is different. Participants in an event will write different speeches, will have different communication formulations. In such cases, the theme, the subject, the key event elements, the entities, the realities are kept, but through accents, markings, highlights, highlights and nuances, ideas of different orientation are constructed. The theme remains, the idea changes. The theme is kept, the idea changes. Communication formulations remain largely convergent in the area of objective meanings. They become divergent in the area of subjective,

humorous meanings. The same amount of knowledge can be poured into several communication formulas. Reality admits several formulations. Each text / speech is a formulation, one of the potential discourses (Voinea, 2020; Sandu, 2021; Rahimian et al., 2022). Saying it is a choice, a decision to put it differently. The wording is a decision about an event and a decision about itself. In relation to the objective event, the decision concerns the amount of knowledge retained, the perspective of ideosocio-moral reporting and the coefficient of ignoring some of the elements of knowledge. Discourse is not only about preserving meanings, but also about ignoring meanings. Ignorance can be voluntary or involuntary. Ignorance also means eliminating objective meanings and replacing them with subjective ones.

In relation to itself, the communication formulation is the application of a rhetorical decision: the register of presentation (positive, negative, neutral), positioning (agreement, rejection, objectivity), assigned vocabulary, recourse to style figures and tropes, structuring, writing (telegraphic, analytical, in the form of editorial, article, phenomenon analysis, etc.). The wording therefore presents two joint articulations: one related to ideation, provided knowledge and another related to rhetoric (thematic approach). The recipient who reads a text, has, thus, at his disposal not the reality, but the wording given by a producer to this reality. In general, as a wording, the text whispers first. The impression is that he speaks vaguely, equivocally, ambiguously. Therefore, in order to understand it properly, it is necessary to read it several times, to put it in several contexts, to approach it in several keys and, as much as possible, to read it in several coordinates and to we exchange impressions. Being whispered, the text takes us where we are able to allow it to take us. However, in its ambiguity, it has an orientation that can only be identified through an objective reading. Objectively, in the universe of textuality, it means a double articulated subjectivity: an authentic and honest subjectivity and a subjectivity tested in the game of subjectivities. Cogitatively, the text carries us through the inferences for which it provides primers. The text / speech proposes, the communicator disposes. The formulation of communicative contents takes place in language and is based on its property of "cognitive compression" (see Damasio & Damasio, 1992).

Interpretation/understanding achieves a cognitive decompression, a significant decompression. The decompressive reading results in an effect of knowledge, of returning to the reality of departure. Eventual formulations are never completely neutral. Those who prove neutral are those who want everything, that is, truth, goodness, and objectivity. They want to capture the truth of the event, of the state, of the situation. The formulations work according to J. Searle's principle of general expressibility: everything can be expressed in language.

3. Understanding the wording and areas of vague, confusing

The text is a construction, it is a functionally oriented mechanism. An idea can find many forms of expression (Teodorescu et al., 2017; Anton et al., 2021; Ciupercă et al., 2022). The communication analysis must start from the reality that for an idea several communication formulations can be found and that the perspective of the one who formulated, his interests, his biases, without him wanting this, leaves room for a better understanding. The recipient must try to understand the text better than his producer understood it. E. Schleirmacher (2002) fixed the axiom that the reader must understand better than the author understood. Each formulation is a perspective, a point of view on an objective message idea. Another wording can bring a better perspective, a significant effect. Sometimes the text shows that either the producer of the text does not know what he is saying, or he is saying something and does not understand what he is saying, or that he is expressing a point of view and, implicitly, accepting a contrary point of view. Categorically, there are two types of texts: some express themselves others express a reality (Armstrong, Hughes & Ferracina, S. 2019; Чернова & Талалаева, 2020; Topor, 2021). The first are imaginary texts and can possibly have an artistic, creative, aesthetic character. The others are informative texts. Any text is capable of generating meaning. Its semantic capital depends on two factors: the immanent textual potential to unfold (textual reserve) and the hermeneutic capacity of the reader communicator (hermeneutic competence). The interpretive interaction between the communicator and the text leads to communicative fission. The amplitude and quality

of the generated meanings is dependent on the two endogenous factors (text, communicator), but also on exogenous, contextual, situational factors. Any reading, any analysis is not strictly dependent on the objective textual reserve. In terms of understanding, interpretation can appear as decoding, decryption, decryption. Depending on the criterion of the explanation, the interpretation can be constituted in illustration, exemplification, description, prescription. In the text you can access several routes, several significant routes. There is a set of paths of evidence, of clear and distinct meanings brought into discourse through a concise language adapted to the object.

There is, on the other hand, a set of paths that magnetize the confusing meanings. In essence, the confusion floats in suspension in the structured text. The suspenseful suspense awaits its structuring. It can be said that no text gets rid of the confusion. Whether textualization means the meaningful formulation of reality or the imaginary. Detextualization is the unfolding, decompression of the text as reality. The fact that some textual communication elements are confusing is a premise on the effect of communicative content.

4. Discourse and reality

Any speech expresses a knowledge of reality. The fact that the one who elaborates the communicative content has at his disposal for expression several semiotic, linguistic, graphic solutions, makes that what the text says is not everything that the producer knows. After all, for the communicator, speech simply means. On the other hand, what the text says contains only a part of what in the set of linguistic possibilities could have been expressed, formulated. As such, there is a good chance that more will be extracted from what has been said than has been said. This is the effect of intrinsic communication content. There is also an extrinsic communication effect. This comes in part from the choices made by analysts about „what techniques give them more meaning.” The methods have a communicative content effect, they lead the communicator to make relevant connections. Another effect is brought by the producer from outside the discourse. This effect capitalizes on databases and fluid knowledge, which is suspended in the communicative environment in connection with the theme and ideation of the text. Suspended elements cause coagulation, integration, magnetization of meanings.

The extrinsic effect comes from outside the discourse: from the efficiency of methods, techniques and procedures of understanding (unstructured or structured), from the exploitation of suspensive knowledge, from critical thinking, from creativity, from unconventional analyzes and from the hermeneutic performance of the communicator. a movement of thinking on two axes: formatting (making it intelligible) and formulating (organizing the intelligible into words, phrases, utterances, speech). Formatting takes place through linguistic operations of giving meaning, assigning meanings, measuring meanings with available lexemes, performing paraphrasing, administering lexical and existential presuppositions, directing paraphrases and summaries, etc.

The formulation includes linguistic operations of meaningful and communicative construction and is the place where rhetoric intervenes, on its coordinate of formulation strategy (Roventă-Frumușani & Stefanel, 2019; Hristea & Colhon, 2020; Anghel, 2021). We find in formulations operations, actions, movements, maneuvers and strategies of implication, of assignment of implication, anaphorization, pronominalization, of placement of deictics, of situational arrangement of discourse, etc. These are elementary operations that lead to the possible rhetorical inscription in discourse on three levels, marked by Granger: the structuring of the linguistic situation, the structuring of units of meaning and the manipulation of codes and registers. The rhetorical aspect, as Granger points out, is mainly about organizing discourse in order to produce, directly or indirectly, an effect (s). The indirect way is to produce a first effect - a certain disposition of the receiver - in order to facilitate or introduce the production of the final effect sought. The auxiliary effect can be effective (arousing an emotion, a mood) or cognitive (evoking knowledge, guiding thinking through analogies and associations, activating a disposition of intelligence). Only occasionally and accidentally is rhetoric exercised in a direct way or causes (and relies on) direct effects of an affective nature. Essentially indirect, it wants to produce a state of receptivity to the philosophical work that discourse expresses. By inciting

movements of thought into concepts - these may at first be concepts of objects designated by the languages of common perception or science, by the severely codified jargon of various professions with a recognized and established status, by more diffuse, less homogeneous cultural languages. symbolically overdetermined. Rhetoric sensitizes the receiver, orients him towards the perception of the linguistic construction of the discourse, overlapping with an inferentially logical or "logical-like" (logicoid), manifest or implicit edification.

5. Fusion and communication fission

In fusion we are dealing with an effect of organizing the objective meanings of texts. The effect takes place through a more precise structuring of the ideation, through the combination, aggregation of the evident and suspensive meanings, implicit ones that are identified in the text. In fission are also captured significant elements invisible in the object-reality described by the text. The fission approach takes knowledge from the knowledge capital of the communicator. The presence and work of this indirect rhetoric can be spotted at several complementary levels, starting with the most superficial: the structuring of linguistic situations. This is the case when using marked compositional dialogue or interrogation. The first effect then consists in figuring out the labor of thought, through the conflict of the protagonists and the evolution of their positions. As for interrogation, it often remains suspended after the receiver is directed in the direction of the direction (Badea, 2017; Csesznek & Coman, 2020; Frunza, 2022; Stănescu; Essameldin, Ismail & Darwish, 2022). The indirect effect is a propaedeutic one. A second level would be that of structuring the units of meaning: the way in which the producer uses the significant contents conveyed by the natural language and notified directly by the receiver. The ordering of these contents together with their non-pertinent aspects gives an „oblique” meaning. The figures of speech intervene here. Finally, a third level at which rhetoric operates could be described as a code maneuver. Although forced to speak, essentially, in the common language, the producer permanently transposes his rules, approaching registers and tonalities specific to the discursive situation. There may even be deliberate changes in the semantic code, indications for the reader of a permanent presence of this modulatory activity.

Textual fission is not a process of mere inference or judgment. Fiction is what Richard J. Heuer attributed to „judgment”: „is what analysts use to fill gaps in their knowledge. It entails going beyond the available information and is the main means of coping with uncertainty. „It is used by analysts to eliminate gaps in their knowledge. It requires penetration beyond the available meanings and is the main way to deal with uncertainty. met him uncertainly” (Heuer, 1999, p. 31).

Textual fusion works with the known. Fusion is a fusion of known meanings into a fusion product consisting of the aggregation, combination, corroboration, grouping, ordering, ranking, and synthesis of known meanings. The main effect of the merger is one of organization. Instead, fission works both with known communicative elements (those resulting from fusion) and with uncertain, contradictory, incomplete meanings. Fission brings in the computational process presuppositions, judgments, inferences, relevant concepts. It makes a leap towards cognitive elements, which can only be found as premises in the fusion product. Fission enters the realm of uncertainty, of the unknown. The main effect of fission is one of communicative creativity resulting from the leap to the unknown.

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